

Conference Abstract

Screening for Pathogens and Studying Bats' Blood and Tissue Microbiome

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Abstract

Bats possess unique physiological adaptations, including thermophysiological flexibility, which enable them to tolerate and harbor diverse pathogens without overt disease. Their ability to sustain powered flight and enter torpor or hibernation contributes to their immune resilience, making them important reservoirs for zoonotic pathogens such as viruses (rabies, Ebola, coronaviruses) and bacteria (*Leptospira*, *Salmonella*, *Bartonella*, *Rickettsia*). Bats' dense social roosting and migratory behaviors facilitate pathogen transmission, underscoring the need for effective surveillance.

This study examined the blood microbiomes of five bat species from the Vespertilionidae and *Rhinolophidae* families inhabiting three caves in northern Bulgaria (Devetashka, Orlova, and Parnicite). Using pooled blood samples (n=120) and two bat hearts, DNA was extracted for microbiome analysis via shotgun metagenomic sequencing, alongside PCR-based detection of human pathogens.

Bacterial phyla and genera distribution varied significantly among bat species, with prominent genera including *Bacillus*, *Mycoplasma*, *Pseudomonas*, and

Sphingobacterium. Alpha diversity, measured by the Simpson index, revealed slightly higher microbial diversity in *Miniopterus schreibersii* and *Myotis myotis*, with no significant differences among cave populations. Principal Coordinates Analysis (PCoA) highlighted distinct microbial community compositions between bat species and cave locations. PCR results identified *Mycobacterium* in 26 of 34 blood samples and in 1 of 2 heart tissue samples, suggesting its prevalence in bat populations. No samples tested positive for *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, *Brucella* spp., *Coxiella burnetii*, or *Toxoplasma gondii*, indicating the absence of these pathogens in the sampled individuals. The detection of atypical *Mycobacteria* and *Brucella* sp. in the bats' blood emphasizes its potential role as an opportunistic pathogen and the need for further investigation into its zoonotic significance. These findings highlight the diversity and zoonotic potential of bat-associated microbiomes, supporting the need for continued pathogen surveillance in bat populations. All metagenomic shotgun sequencing data were published at NCBI Sequence Read Archive under the bioproject number PRJNA1215671.

Keywords

zoonoses, bat blood, and tissue microbiome, mNGS (new genome sequencing metagenomics), PCR

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.